

Micellar Properties of the Zwitterionic Detergents 'CHAPS' and 'CHAPSO' used in Membrane Biochemistry

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The micellar properties of the zwitterionic detergent 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)-dimethylammonio]-1-propane-sulphonate (common name CHAPS) and its 2-hydroxy derivative, CHAPSO, are described. These form micelles above 8 mM in water, have a molecular area at the interface of around 160 Å² (CHAPS) and 120 Å² (CHAPSO), and appear to be arranged in stacks, similar to the bile salts. CHAPS is shown to be totally inert towards a globular protein, and to be able to essentially quantitatively solubilise liver microsome cytochrome P-450.

HJELMELAND has introduced to membrane biochemistry two non-denaturing zwitterionic detergents, 3-[(3-cholamidopropyl)dimethylammonio]-1-propanesulphonate (formula I, trivial name CHAPS) and its 2-hydroxy derivative (formula II, suggested trivial name CHAPSO), and has described some of their solubilising abilities^{1,2}. Of the two, CHAPS has been used to date more widely to solubilise a variety of membrane bound proteins^{1,3,4} and CHAPSO is also expected to be popular soon since it is reported to be twice as effective as CHAPS in solubilising active opiate receptors and since it is also commercially available now. Comparison of CHAPS and CHAPSO with other traditional detergents used in membrane biochemistry (e.g. Triton X-100, Lubrol PX, bile salts and *N*-alkyl sulphobetaines) has proved the former to be more benign and efficient extracting agents. Some of the physical properties of these detergents have been reported by Hjelmeland *et al.*⁵. In light of their expected wide use, we thought it worthwhile to study some of the physicochemical and biophysical properties of CHAPS and CHAPSO in solution.

Experimental

A sample of CHAPS (Fluka) was used as received. CHAPSO (Calbiochem) was a gift from Dr. Hjelmeland. Conductivity measurements were made using a Digisun bridge at 301 K. Surface tension measurements were made with a Fischer tensiometer using a platinum ring. The surface area

per molecule was calculated by using the Gibbs isotherm method, as illustrated by Osipow⁶. Fluorescence spectra were recorded on a Hitachi 650-10S spectrofluorimeter. CD spectra of the proteins (Sigma) were recorded, in the presence and absence of CHAPS, using a JASCO-J20 instrument and ellipticity (θ) expressed in millidegree. All measurements were made at ambient temperature around 300 K and in 1 cm pathlength quartz cells.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 1 shows the concentration dependent variation in the specific conductance of an aqueous solution of CHAPS; the biphasic plot shows a break at $(c)^{1/2} = 0.051$, i.e., $c = 2.6$ mM. Such plots are typical of charged surfactants that aggregate beyond a certain molarity (the critical micelle concentration or cmc) in water⁶ and Fig. 1 suggests

Fig. 1. Variation of the conductance (Δ) of CHAPS with its concentration (c) in H₂O.

the cmc of CHAPS to be around 2.6 mM. The conductivity of CHAPS beyond cmc agrees with the value reported by Hjelmeland¹. The tensiometric behaviour of the detergent is shown in Fig. 2. The surface tension drops rapidly between 0 and 3 mM CHAPS in water, and beyond 5 mM it is essentially

Fig. 2. The dependence of surface tension (γ) on the concentration of CHAPS in H_2O . The inset shows the variation of γ with $\log [CHAPS]$.

constant at about 42 dynes cm^{-1} . The estimated cmc by this method is around 2.8 mM at 301 K. The absence of any extremum in any part of the curve in Fig. 2 indicates that the sample of CHAPS is free of any surface active impurity. An estimation of the surface area per molecule of the detergent is possible if one follows the variation of the surface tension with $\log c$ and uses the Gibbs adsorption isotherm⁶ as

$$\Gamma = -\frac{1}{2RT} \frac{d\gamma}{d \ln c}; \quad A = \frac{10^{16}}{N\Gamma}$$

where, γ , c and Γ denote the surface tension in $dyne\ cm^{-1}$, the bulk concentration of the zwitterionic surfactant in molarity units, and the surface excess in $mol\ cm^{-2}$. The surface area per molecule, A , is related to Γ through Avogadro number N as above and expressed in units of \AA^2 . The variation of γ with $\log c$ was obtained from the rectilinear portions of this plot below cmc (inset in Fig. 2) and the area per molecule of CHAPS calculated to be $157\ \text{\AA}^2$ in water at 301 K. A similar study on CHAPSO in water yielded its surface area per molecule to be $122\ \text{\AA}^2$ —a value slightly smaller than that of CHAPS, presumably a condensation effect due to the 2-OH moiety of CHAPSO. Comparison of these values with those of cholic acid and deoxycholic acid films in water (mean value of $148\ \text{\AA}^2$ and $113\ \text{\AA}^2$, respectively⁷, suggests that like these two molecules, the molecules of CHAPS and of CHAPSO arrange themselves at the water interface with all the hydroxyl groups and the ionic groups in contact

with water. This similarity also lets us expect that in micelles of CHAPS and of CHAPSO in water, the individual molecules will aggregate in a 'stacked' fashion just as in the case of the deoxycholate or cholate micelles⁷.

The microenvironmental polarity in these two micelles is also comparable to that of deoxycholate micelles, as the following experiment reveals. The polarity of a micelle can be monitored by following the fluorescence properties of pyrene solubilised in the assembly. Specifically, the ratio of the fluorescence intensities of the third and the first vibronic components of the emission band of monomeric pyrene around 370-400 nm, *i.e.* the ratio I_3/I_1 , has been shown to be sensitive to the polarity of the medium⁸⁻¹⁰ and has been used to determine both the cmc and the micellar polarity. Fig. 3 shows the variation of the intensity ratio I_3/I_1 of pyrene monomer as a function of the CHAPS concentration,

Fig. 3. The variation of the pyrene fluorescence intensity ratio I_3/I_1 , as a function of $[CHAPS]$ in H_2O . I_3 and I_1 are the intensities of the third and first vibronic compounds, respectively of the emission band of monomeric pyrene around 390 nm: (●) CHAPS in H_2O (x) CHAPS in 0.5 M NaCl. The plot of CHAPSO in H_2O essentially coincided with that of CHAPS in H_2O .

both in pure water and in the presence of 0.5 M NaCl. The ratio increases from a value of 0.6 in the absence of CHAPS, sigmoidally, to a limiting value of around 1.2 beyond 8 mM CHAPS. It is noteworthy that the cmc estimated using this curve (*i.e.* $\sim 8\ mM$) is somewhat higher than 3 mM reported above, but is in agreement with the reported⁵ value of 8 mM. The CHAPSO system yielded an identical plot, with a cmc 8 mM, a value that agrees with the earlier report⁵ for this detergent. It is likely that the values of below 3 mM obtained for the cmc of CHAPS by conductance and surface

tension indicate pre-micellar aggregates but there is no rigorous proof for this possibility yet. The addition of 0.5 M NaCl appears to lower the cmc value of CHAPS somewhat, but the limiting value of I_3/I_1 is unchanged upon salt addition. This value of about 1.2 obtained in both CHAPS, CHAPSO micelles, when compared with the value of about 1.4 that we found in deoxycholate micelles (only slightly changed upon salt-addition), and 1.1 found in SDS micelles (decreasing to 1.0 upon NaCl addition) suggests that the CHAPS and CHAPSO systems offer a less polar environment to the solubilised pyrene than SDS, and a more polar environment than deoxycholate micelles. The polarity of the CHAPS type of micelles roughly corresponds to that of *n*-butyl ether ($E_T \sim 33.4$) while that of deoxycholate is a little lower and that of SDS micelles resemble benzene, toluene or monohalobenzenes ($E_T \sim 37.5$). While there is no rigorous proof for this yet, it appears that the lower polarity of CHAPS (and CHAPSO) *vis-a-vis* SDS might be related to the differences in their micellar packing and head-group dispositions. It is also likely that while the packing and aggregation properties of the CHAPS group of micelles and of bile salt micelles might be similar, the enhanced polarity of the former might be because of the presence of the zwitterionic groups in contrast to bile salts which have only the anionic carboxylates as head-groups. Pyrene is known to be located in the head-group region of micelles and to have preferential interactions with quaternary ammonium moieties¹¹ which might place it a little differently in CHAPS and in CHAPSO micelles in comparison with cholate or other anionic micelles. We, therefore, tentatively conclude that the shape and packing in the present cases is not very different from that of the bile salts. This similarity and also the ionic strength dependence of the cmc (Fig. 3) suggests that CHAPS might have an aggregation number similar to bile salts, which might increase upon salt addition. Hjelmeland *et al.*⁵ have reported aggregation numbers of 10 and 11 for CHAPS and CHAPSO, respectively. Table 1 compares the micellar properties of these two detergents with those of some bile salts and of SDS.

TABLE 1—COMPARATIVE MICELLAR PROPERTIES OF SOME SURFACTANTS

Surfactant	cmc mM	Interfacial area per molecule Å ²	Polarity estima-	Aggrega-
			ted by pyrene fluorescence* E_T	
CHAPS	8 (~3 ?)	157	~33.4	10
CHAPSO	8	132	~33.4	11
Na-cholate	10*** (pH 8-9)	148	—	2
Na-deoxy- cholate	2***	113	<32	2
SDS	8	38	~37.5	62

* Rough estimates based on Ref. 10. ** From Ref. 5.
*** From *Methods Enzymol.*, 1979, 56, 784.

That these detergents are inert towards globular protein conformations, is illustrated in Fig. 4, where one notices no change in the circular dichroism spectrum of ribonuclease upon the addition of the detergent CHAPS. We next studied the membrane protein cytochrome P-450, which was initially

Fig. 4. CD spectrum of ribonuclease (0.116 mg ml⁻¹): (x) solubilised in 12 mM CHAPS and (O) in H₂O.

investigated by Hjelmeland, in order to determine the extent of solubilisation into CHAPS micelles by extracting the protein from liver microsomes. In a typical experiment, animals were injected with phenobarbitone (8 mg/100 g body weight) to induce cytochrome P-450 and their liver processed to isolate microsomes. The microsomes (20 mg) were solubilised in a buffer solution containing 10 mM Tris (pH 7.6), 1 mM EDTA and 1% (w/v) sodium cholate to which 0.1 M NaCl was added in a proportion to give 3 mg cholate per mg protein (6 ml buffer). The mixture was stirred in ice for 15 min and centrifuged at 105 000 × g for 2 h. The supernatant was used to measure the total protein¹² and the cytochrome P-450 content¹³ extracted into the cholate micelles. In a second experiment, the buffer solution contained 10 mM CHAPS in place of cholate under otherwise identical conditions of workup and estimation. Cholate extraction yielded 63.4% of total protein solubilised and 71% (17.04 nM in absolute amounts) of cytochrome P-450 solubilised, while CHAPS was found to be distinctly better in that it could extract 89.3% of total protein and 92% (22.08 nM) of cytochrome P-450. Optical features of the CHAPS-extracted cytochrome P-450 suggest the protein to be essentially native in conformation.

In conclusion, CHAPS and CHAPSO are seen to be efficient detergents for solubilising membrane

proteins and their advantages are their inertness towards protein conformation, their zwitterionic nature and the low polarity environment that they offer to solubilisates.

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Note added in Proof :

R. E. STARK, P. D. LEFF, S. G. MILHEIM and A. KROFF (*J. Phys Chem.*, 1984, **88**, 6063) have determined the cmc of CHAPS to be 11 mM and aggregation number to be 4 by the nmr method, and have suggested that it forms dimers at around 3 mM.